

Proposing Software Solutions to Address Coding and Deployment Challenges for ML/AI Researchers

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Introduction

AI serves as a powerful catalyst for innovation, enabling the development of cutting-edge technologies and solutions that enhance efficiency and address complex challenges across various industries. This is not just limited to fields like chemistry, physics, and molecular biology, but also includes fields such as mathematics and even geology. For this reason, research across all domains is placing increasing importance on computing in a broad sense, particularly within the realm of AI/ML, and it is imperative to make research more accessible and efficient in order to uncover solutions to new problems.

Most researchers working across different domains are not experts in computer science and must deal with a large amount of data, which is not trivial. Processing this data requires a large amount of computational power, which can be tough to acquire, and then to use. Additionally, since these researchers learn about machine learning concepts in different disciplines, projects, and teams, the patterns they use for designing their code are often not standardized. The lack of standardization is evident from how dissimilar teams prefer different methods to track their research results and share them with their teams. Lastly, different patterns of model development make the task for the deployment teams much more complex, which eventually leads to difficulties during maintenance of the service.

The objective of this study is to propose software solutions for researchers across the UIUC campus facing code maintainability and deployment issues in projects working with AI/ML. During this work, researchers were interviewed to understand their needs and the challenges they face during their work, and this data was analyzed to scope broader problems. Subsequently, a review of the various free and open-source tools that could potentially solve these challenges was done, and a proof-of-concept of one of the identified solutions, called “Metaflow” was deployed. The last stage of this study was to collect feedback from the stakeholders and understand if the identified tool could help improve research productivity. The following phases were derived from the mentioned goals:

1. **Planning & Analysis:** This phase involved understanding the researchers' pain points with the help of interviews and past experiences. The next step was to focus only on the more generalizable problems, which impact a broader audience.
2. **Exploration:** This phase involved exploring the best available free and open-source software that fulfilled the needs and helped tackle the problems.
3. **Design & Development:** This phase involved all the tasks related to the design and development of the infrastructure required to deploy the chosen product and working towards a proof-of-concept to gain a deeper understanding of the tool.
4. **Testing & Feedback:** This phase included testing the deployed tool and collecting researchers' feedback through interviews.

Phase 1: Planning & Analysis

The following steps were conducted to identify research problems and reduce them to a generalizable problem statement.

Identifying Researchers

A set of researchers were identified across the UIUC campus who were working on a wide range of research problems that used AI/ML and were willing to volunteer their time.

Planning Interviews

We prepared structured interviews [1][2] with a predefined set of questions and scheduled the interview meetings. The questions were defined to be able to understand the research goal and the stage of ML model deployment (data collection, data cleaning, model training, and deployment). If the researcher was aware of any problems they were facing or they could foresee, we conducted a deep dive into the problem. Otherwise, we would ask questions related to different aspects of the project, encouraging them to think in different directions (like data storage, data versioning and access, team collaboration, code maintenance, deliverables, public deployment). These questions were inspired by [4]. Appendix A provides more details on how the interviews were conducted.

Interviews

We identified two researchers, and scheduled interviews with them. The following sections describe the interview experiences and the inferences derived from those.

Interview 1

The researcher worked on a project at the intersection of chemistry, engineering, and biomedical science with a goal of detecting spatial location in molecule images. They were in the initial experimentation phase of model development. They mentioned that these images were more than 1 billion pixels (approximately 800-900 megabytes) each. They also mentioned that they must constantly move their work from their local machine to a virtual machine with

better computing capabilities, and that moving the large-sized images was time-consuming. Additionally, they shared that the virtual machine was a shared resource and therefore not available all the time. On enquiring about how they did machine learning experimentation, they said that they usually tracked the parameters and results for each experiment using a simple Word document. If they wanted to share results with their team, they added it to a cloud-based file system and shared it. If the size of the results to be shared was too big, they shared the virtual machine itself.

Inferences from Interview 1

We identified the following problems from the first interview, which can be generalized to a broader audience:

1. There is a need for a large amount of computing power that is easily accessible and available so that researchers don't have to wait for the VMs to become available.
2. There is a need for a way to share data between local and virtual machines easily (perhaps a place from where data can be accessed by both types of machines).
3. There is a need for better methods of tracking parameters and results when experimenting with a machine learning model.
4. There is a need for an easy, more illustrative way to share the work within the teams.

Interview 2

The researcher was a chemist working on predicting ideal conditions for reactions to produce the optimum yield. They had already trained the machine learning model and were in the phase of making the tool open to the public. Therefore, the problems they shared in their interview were very different from the ones that were shared in the first interview. The researcher was already developing a container environment such that their model could easily be used for generating inferences, and shared concerns about the development process. They were also not sure how that containerized environment could be used by anyone accessing the tool over the internet. Related to this problem itself, the researcher shared the need for a web interface that might allow anyone lacking computer science know-how to use their model.

Inferences from Interview 2

We identified the following problems from the second interview, which can be generalized to a broader audience:

1. There is a need to make the containerization of the machine learning model easier or eliminate it altogether.
2. There is a need for a way to orchestrate the containerized version of the machine learning model.
3. There is a need for an easy way to generate a front-end web interface that can allow people over the internet to use the model.

Deriving from Others' Experiences

Experiences from MMLI

The problems identified through this interview were reinforced through the experiences derived from the [Molecule Maker Lab Institute](#) project at [NCSA](#). In particular, the need for a containerized environment, an orchestrator to manage the execution of these containers, and a front-end interface has been observed in many of the tools that the Software team at NCSA has deployed. [3] mentions one such project.

The team often notices researchers following non-standard patterns for developing their models and services. A simple example which the team has witnessed is a container that is spun up for each inference (after which it is destroyed) versus a container that has a long running service in it taking up multiple requests. These inconsistencies led to non-standard deployment models, which required planning and design work and therefore incurred more time. Additionally, different models are harder to maintain as it is difficult to keep track of which service follows what model. The following problems can be identified from these experiences:

1. There is a need for a framework or a standard pattern for machine learning model development that can be recommended to the various research groups across the campus which can greatly help in cutting down the deployment time.
2. There is a need for a multipurpose orchestrator service that can handle the execution of containerized or non-containerized services for different projects.

Knowledge Share with Illinois Computes Program

The study found an interesting collaboration opportunity with the Illinois Computes program at NCSA. [Illinois Computes](#) (IC) is a program with \$50-million of funding allocated towards offering resources and expertise to researchers to help them improve the efficiency of their research. IC has been working on finding the best ways to invest this funding and therefore has been trying to understand the needs of researchers, similar to what this work wanted to achieve in this phase.

The team had released a [survey](#) to do the same and the results could have accelerated this phase of this work. However, due to the timeline of that survey, its results will not impact this work. The aforementioned problems that came up in the interviews were shared in the Illinois Computes weekly sync and it became clear how prevalent these problems are, as other researchers and managers of various projects at NCSA supported the findings. In fact, some researchers shared how they have been working on finding solutions to similar problems and even shared tools that they have been using.

IC provides an opportunity for a bigger impact that can be generated through this study as the results will be reported to the IC team, along with the report.

Problem Narrowing

Proceeding with the analysis part of this phase, the problems discovered through the interviews and experiences were segregated in two phases of research projects:

1. Training, Experimentation, Parameter Tuning Phase: This is the phase of utmost importance to the researchers, and they want to achieve quick results to advance their research. This is where they want to make the tracking of parameters, results, and versioning of artifacts easier, in order to reduce the overhead of doing all these tasks. Additionally, they want to reduce collaboration efforts and ultimately, make the collaboration pipeline seamless. Lastly, they want to be able to access a large amount of computational power easily and scale the training process.
2. Deployment, Monitoring & Maintenance Phase: Not all research projects go through this phase, but most projects have some kind of deliverables involved. Researchers often don't plan this phase, which leads to the problems from the previous "Experimentation" phase seeping in and making this even more complex. This phase can be made easy by using a standard framework or patterns in the previous phase, in coordination with a common deployment strategy. The requirement of a front-end interface for the end users of a public-facing ML model is considered out of the scope of this work.

Figure 1: Problem Narrowing

Challenges

As speculated, the "Planning & Analysis" phase of this work took the maximum amount of time to be completed. This is attributed to the following problems:

1. Limited Availability of Volunteers: Since this work required interviewing volunteers in synchronous meetings, scheduling these instances caused a major challenge primarily because researchers have limited bandwidth.
2. Small Dataset of Interviews: The number of interviews scheduled for the study was limited, which led to the risk of analysis being incorrect. However, due to the limited timeframe of the study, the next "Exploration" phase was initiated.

Phase 2: Exploration

The goal of the exploration phase was to find a free & open-source machine learning operations tool that helped during the experimentation phase and smoothly transitioned into deployment. The market is full of tools that solve these problems. We explored many tools during this phase, some of which already were in use at NCSA. Since each of these tools had a steep learning curve, we based the comparisons on documentation and articles on the internet.

Existing Tools at NCSA

MLflow

[MLflow](#) is a tool developed by Databricks that can be used for most of the problems discussed in the previous section. This tool is being used by several projects at NCSA and a tracking server (which performs the task of tracking the results and artifacts) has already been set up. By adding a few lines of code to the existing experimentation code, tracking of experiments, results, and artifacts can easily be enabled. The experimentation features provided are very helpful and have an intuitive user interface; however, this provides fewer features on the deployment side. Another drawback is that collaboration in MLflow is non-trivial. Even though there is a component of MLflow called [MLflow Projects](#) that enables packaging machine learning code in a reusable and reproducible way, it provides a less strict framework as compared to what is needed to standardize the deployment process.

C3 AI Platform

The [C3 AI offering](#) is an end-to-end solution for building, deploying, and operating enterprise AI applications. This is being used by several projects at NCSA. C3 AI has a funding process in which they accept proposals and fund research projects. This also provides solutions to most of the problems which were identified but since it's a paid offering, it was not considered as an option for this study.

Other Tools Explored

Many other tools were explored, some of which offered solutions to only a subset of problems, while some provided end-to-end solutions with some subtle differences. Tools like Neptune.ai, Comet, and MLflow only solved the experimentation side of the problem, and therefore were not explored further. Other tools explored were [Metaflow](#), [Kubeflow](#), and [Hugging Face](#). In this list, Hugging Face has a free tier with limited features, but it can't be deployed on-prem to take advantage of all its features. Thus, a comprehensive comparison between Metaflow and Kubeflow was done.

Both Metaflow and Kubeflow are powerful machine learning operations (MLOps) platforms that can be used for experimentation, development, and production. Metaflow is a Python library that helps data scientists build and manage data science projects while Kubeflow is a Kubernetes-based toolkit for end-to-end management of ML workflows. Both platforms are open

source, Python-based, which can be deployed on-premises, and offer parallel execution of tasks, and a user interface for tracking the workflows.

Differences between the two tools [6][7] exist in the following areas:

1. Use case: If the use case is to handle production workloads, then Metaflow provides better features. Kubeflow is better if a team is looking for tools that make the lives of ML engineers easier.
2. Communication within workflows: Communication between Metaflow steps is trivial and fast because they are Python functions passing data to each other. However, this makes it harder to pass complex data. On the other hand, communication between Kubeflow pipelines is done through files which are much more versatile though slower.
3. Infrastructure needs: Metaflow is more cloud-friendly and provides helm charts for deployment on a Kubernetes cluster. Kubeflow just needs Kubernetes to be set up which can be deployed easily on any on-premises cluster. This deployment, however, was not done in this study.

After this careful comparison of the available tools and features that each offer, Metaflow was picked as the best choice for end-to-end pipelines since it offers more support for production workloads, and its deployment was planned for the next phase.

Phase 3: Design & Development

In this phase, we deployed Metaflow and ran an ML workflow on it as a proof of concept. This phase also aided me in diving deeply into the product's features, owing to the hands-on experience of the tool. Most of the features that Metaflow provides are captured by Figure 2 and each can be categorized as solutions to either the experimentation or the deployment part of the problems.

Figure 2: Metaflow Features [15]

Deployment

We made several attempts to deploy Metaflow on NCSA's on-prem Kubernetes cluster but none were successful because of poor documentation and support. The next strategy was to deploy Metaflow on a single-node Kubernetes cluster on a local machine, but this also encountered issues due to incomplete documentation lacking proper steps and configuration. A considerable amount of time was spent learning about Metaflow and its features and concepts before initiating the deployment, so it was hard to move to another tool because of the limited timeframe of the study. An understanding was developed that Metaflow is not very mature as of now and currently lacks proper support for on-premises deployments. This led us to explore alternative approaches.

After some analysis, we found that Metaflow provides elaborate and updated documentation for cloud-based deployments like Azure, Amazon Web Services and Google Cloud Platform. Ultimately, Azure was used to perform the deployment and a proof of concept with a simple model training code was demonstrated. The deployment was done using this [documentation](#).

Metaflow Experimentation Demonstration

The demonstration shows a simple machine learning model training example without using any library like Metaflow and goes on to explain the problems that may occur when the code becomes more complex, closer to what production codebases look like. Going forward, it shows how Metaflow can be run locally and be integrated into the same example consisting of training a neural network on the [CIFAR 10](#) dataset. The next section of the demo shows how a simple flag can be used to send the computation to the cloud (Azure Kubernetes Service in our case) and that demonstrates how complex experiments can benefit from the scale Metaflow provides. The last part of the demonstration shows how all the data tracked during the Flow runs can be accessed using Metaflow's simple API. The demonstration can be found on this [link](#). The code files used for the demo are present in [this repository](#).

During the deployment on Azure as well, Metaflow showed signs of immaturity as the flow demonstrated couldn't be run on Azure but was running locally. This was perhaps an unhandled bug related to Metaflow's inability to handle a particular Python version, which could only be resolved after reaching out to their support team.

Metaflow for Production Workloads

Metaflow can easily be used for production workloads by simply modeling the production pipelines as Flows. For example, similar to the training flow described in the demonstration above, another inference flow can be set up. There are more advantages of using it for production traffics:

1. Dependencies are easily handled, because of the dependency decorators (@conda and @conda-base) that Metaflow offers.

2. The same remote datastore (Azure Blob Storage, S3, or Minio) can be used to store both the inputs and outputs for any user request, improving the access to that data as well.
3. Flows can be scheduled enabling the development of flows which may have to run periodically like re-training of a model.
4. Communication between different Flows can allow developing more complex designs for complicated use cases.
5. Using the integration with Argo Workflows, a single command is enough to deploy a model.

Phase 4: Testing & Feedback

The last phase of this study was to collect feedback from the various researchers. We shared the demonstration video, documents and findings with them and compiled a list of simple questions to answer. These questions focused on understanding the following:

1. The features of Metaflow that the researcher might find to be the most helpful
2. Understanding if their work can easily be modeled as a Metaflow “Flow”
3. Understanding if they would want to invest in learning a new tool/library if it gives them access to development support, powerful compute, easy collaboration and reduced time to production
4. Problems they think Metaflow is not able to solve
5. Other tools which they believe can solve the problems in a better way

The following feedback was received from the researchers.

Interview 1 Feedback

The researcher in the first interview believes that Metaflow’s versioning and tracking of all intermediate and final artifacts is the most helpful feature. They also feel that the flows are generalizable enough and researchers will be open to learning this.

We are still working on collecting feedback from other researchers.

Conclusion

To conclude, the study started with understanding the bottlenecks researchers face while working with machine learning. We targeted the more generalizable problems and explored software solutions which may be able to solve these. We deployed the selected tool called Metaflow, and went on to demonstrate the features which researchers might find helpful. Lastly and currently, we are collecting feedback from the researchers to understand the feasibility of the tool in action. The feedback that was received so far shows that the tool can improve research efficiency for researchers.

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Appendices

Appendix A: Structured Interview Conducted for the Planning & Analysis Phase

Structure of the Interviews

- Interviewer introduces themselves.
- Interviewer explains a bit about the goals of the Independent Study and tells the interviewer how it could benefit their projects.
- Interviewer shares that they will be taking notes during the meeting
- Brief introduction of the research project is requested (with domain specific terms abstracted)
- Sharing with them some directions where we can explore possible issues.
- Manual processes like data analysis, writing repeatable code, etc.
- Processes taking a long time like testing, deployment, etc.
- Expensive or old technology
- Problems related to data curation, sharing, or versioning.
- Deploying code for public use, problems related to security/authentication.
- Collaboration in the team including knowledge transfer, sharing work and progress.
- Start asking the following questions:
- Do they already have known problems? If yes, the interviewer dives deeper into it.
- If not, start asking questions below to understand the stage of their project and the processes that they follow.
- Tips:
 - Don't interrupt, wait for them to finish before asking follow up questions
 - Take notes

Potential Interview Questions

1. What is the goal of your project?
2. What phase of ML model development is your project in?
 1. Problem Definition
 2. Data Collection
 3. Data Preprocessing
 4. Model training
 5. Deployment
3. Can you identify 2-3 major problems during any of these steps?
Problems can be related to (just to help them think in different directions):
 1. Any tedious manual processes - eg. writing repeated code, doing manual analysis of some data
 2. Time taking processes like testing, deployment.
 3. Expensive technology being used which is not financially viable.
 4. Dependency on some technology which is slow/too old/less supported.
 5. CI/CD
4. Can you provide concrete examples of these issues in your project?
5. Do you intend to deploy your model to production? If yes,
 1. What is the approximate number of users for the deployed model?
 2. Do we intend to deploy the model for scale or only for a POC? Are there any challenges to scale that you can identify?

If they are unable to identify concrete problems: Drill down into the processes they use and try to look for improvements.